

Diversity- responsive educators

Professionalise yourself!

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Responsiveness to diversity

is a way of approaching diversity that implies a deliberate stance towards promoting equity, inclusion, and social justice; and, thus, towards **reducing inequality**.

Approaching diversity

occurs in every interaction automatically. It can (in)directly strengthen, perpetuate, or reduce inequalities.

One's frame of reference affects one's way of approaching diversity. It is **never neutral**.

Diversity

is a fact, a phenomenon that is part of every society and has always been part of societies.

The identity markers on which people can differ from one another are innumerable.

Social inequality

is also a fact and, moreover, it is the context in which diversity is manifested.

Sociohistorical mechanisms systematically put some at a disadvantage while providing advantages to others.

Why?

Various **societal developments** contribute to an increasing pressure on education professionals to act in a diversity-responsive manner. At the same time, **educational developments** also contribute to this.

- * Increased human rights discourse and policy (e.g., *inclusive education via UN and EU*).
- * Migration increases (in)visible diversity.
- * Globalisation of social movements.
- * Dissemination of intersectional thinking.

- * Increase of various educational needs.
- * Persistent educational inequality.
- * Teachers feel underprepared.
- * Ongoing teacher shortages.

Double responsibility for educators:

- ▶ Foster **students'** diversity-responsive attitudes and practices
- ▶ **Leading by example** through own practices from a societal role.

Professionalise yourself

1

Determine learning goals

Assess what you are already do and can still do to become more diversity-responsive.

- ▶ Rate yourself in this tool.

2

Install accountability

Install incentives to keep working towards your learning goal.

- ▶ Plan peer-coach meetings.

3

Search for inspiration

Delving into materials regarding your own learning goal.

- ▶ Consult tools and cooleagues.

Why?

Structural training or **education** to become an educator (in higher education) is scarce to non-existent. Educators are therefore often **left to their own devices** to translate ad-hoc training initiatives or workshops to effective professional development. Literature on design principles for effective professionalisation must be consulted. Some important elements are detailed below:

Design principles

- Content is **coherent** (framework-based), **evidence-informed** and related to **educator practices**.
- It is **spread** over time over at least 20h.
- **Self-reflection** and **action** are initiated.
- Participants have **ownership** to make choices on their focus and process based on their own needs.
- Professional learning happens in the **work context**.
- **Learning communities** are created.
- Time to professionalise is **proactively secured**.
- **Prior experience** and **informel learning** are valued.
- The **trainer or supporter** is high-quality.

Being an educator

Why are you an educator?

What are **important values** for you? How are these values manifested in your role as an educator?

What is the meaning of **qualitative education** for you?

What is your **role as an educator** within diversity-responsive education?

Practices

1

CHALLENGE ONE'S OWN FRAMES OF REFERENCE

2

CREATE SAFE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

3

INTEGRATE INCLUSIVE PEDAGOGY AND LEARNING MATERIALS

4

CHALLENGE STUDENTS' FRAMES OF REFERENCE

5

EXPLICITLY MODEL DIVERSITY-RESPONSIVE PRACTICES

6

RAISE RESPONSIVENESS TO DIVERSITY IN SOCIETY

CHALLENGE ONE'S OWN FRAMES OF REFERENCE

1.1 You deliberately reflect on values you find important or evident in your professional situation and how your (privileged) position in society and previous experiences contribute to this.

1.2 You consciously empathise with the living situation of people who are very different from you (e.g., conversation, film, book...).

1.3 You explore the ideas of thinkers and scholars from minoritised groups within your field.

1.4 You explore mechanisms that maintain or reduce social inequality.

1.5 You take a clear stance on sensitive topics and can substantiate why they do or do not contribute to responsiveness to diversity.

1.6 You take targeted action to expose your blind spots (e.g., asking for feedback on your behaviour, discussion with people with different opinions, professionalisation...).

1.7 You reflect on the impact of your own practices and take targeted action to make your teaching more diversity-responsive.

Question for reflection: How much of your **mental space** is occupied by worries about not being able to be yourself, not belonging or facing prejudice by others? (*color in*)

2

CREATE SAFE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

2.1 You integrate activities into your teaching assignment that focus on getting to know each other and group bonding.

2.2 You create opportunities to get to know your students and their personal contexts better.

2.3 You adopt an equal attitude towards your students and share with them your own values, experiences and vulnerabilities that are professionally relevant.

2.4 You use learning activities where everyone can be heard in an approachable way.

2.5 You create a clear framework on code of conduct and engage in dialogue with your students about them.

2.6 You address students on behaviour that goes against the agreed code of conduct and frame why this is not acceptable.

2.7 You respond to strong emotions, resistance or mutual disagreement so that everyone feels heard and respected.

Question for reflection: What do **you need** to feel safe as an educator? From your students? From your institution?

3

INTEGRATE INCLUSIVE PEDAGOGY AND LEARNING MATERIALS

3.1 You design learning materials with attention to representation, counterstereotypical imagery and inclusive language.

3.2 You recognise and integrate knowledge and perspectives of underrepresented groups in your field.

3.3 You attune your teaching to the baseline situation of your students and actively seek input and feedback from them.

3.4 You incorporate variation and choice in terms of teaching materials, learning materials and supporting facilities.

3.5 You use learning activities in which students must work together, inherently aimed at learning to improve mutual cooperation.

3.6 You make your (final) assessment of a student on multiple moments and forms of evaluation.

Question for reflection: What other **learning activities** do you use to work inclusively?

4

CHALLENGE STUDENTS' FRAMES OF REFERENCE

4.1 You deliberately make students reflect on values they find important or evident and how their (privileged) position and previous experiences have contributed to this.

4.2 You use learning activities in which students empathise with the living situation of people who are different from them.

4.3 You make students reflect on points of views or actions, from their own or others, that maintain or reinforce existing social inequalities.

4.4 You make students aware that content provided can always be approached from multiple perspectives and that what is highlighted is contingent in nature.

4.5 You respond to stereotypical thinking, prejudice and discriminatory behaviour of students and engage constructively with them about it.

4.6 In your teaching assignment, you deliberately seek entrances to discuss potentially sensitive topics with students and facilitate discussion.

Question for reflection: Which societal **sensitive topics** could you integrate in your course?

5

EXPLICITLY MODEL DIVERSITY-RESPONSIVE PRACTICES

5.1 You make students aware of diversity-responsive practices you consciously set up in your teaching and explain why.

5.2 You discuss with students what they themselves perceive as diversity-responsive in your actions.

Question for reflection: When would you **rather avoid** to make explicit your diversity-responsive practices? Why?

6

RAISE RESPONSIVENESS TO DIVERSITY IN SOCIETY

6.1 You discuss with colleagues what responsiveness to diversity can entail in your teaching or the broader work field.

6.2 In formal board meetings within your program or institution, you notice negative forms of approaching diversity (those that reinforce inequity) and engage in dialogue about it.

6.3 In your contacts with people from the work field, you notice negative forms of approaching diversity and engage in dialogue about them.

6.4 In the public debate about (higher) education, you take a stance towards diversity-responsive education.

6.5 Potential research assignments are executed in a diversity-responsive manner and you actively disseminate findings that encourage responsiveness to diversity.

Question for reflection: How did you take up your societal role as an educator **in the past**?

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Plan of action

What are your three **strongest practices**? What will you do concretely to keep using these strengths in the future?

1

2

3

Regarding what practices are you able and willing **to grow**?

What are possible **quick wins** you could implement immediately?
What are you willing to try out?

Choose at least **one focus (practice)** for your professional learning in the near and concrete future.

- Why you choose this focus?
- What is your own goal?
- How will you know if your goal is reached?
- What do you need to reach your goal?
- Who could help you to reach your goal?
- What could be your first step?
- How much time can you spend on it?
- When will you spend time on it?

Who is allowed to support and coach you along the way?

Empty rounded rectangular box for writing the answer to the question "Who is allowed to support and coach you along the way?"

When will you meet up with this person?

After a meeting: What are new insights? What needs **redirection**?

Large empty rounded rectangular box for writing the answer to the question "After a meeting: What are new insights? What needs redirection?"

Extra writing space

Adjacent material

Background research presentation

Online environment
with links and inspiration

SUPPORT FROM

 benjamin.ponet@ugent.be

 Benjamin Ponet

 ResearchgateBenjamin Ponet

 www.lopo.ugent.be